

An Evaluation of Tourism Education in Nigeria's Higher Institutions

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Abstract—This paper evaluated the quality of tourism education in Nigeria higher education. The problem of poor quality of tourism education in Nigeria's higher institutions prompted the study. Archival research was used with evaluation reports as secondary data, twenty evaluation reports for different polytechnics from the National board for technical education (NBTE) from 1995-2012 were assessed. The evidence from the documents shows that the quality of teaching and evaluation is fair. The programmes resources are fairly good, and most of the teachers do not have a postgraduate qualification in tourism related courses. It is therefore recommended that the institutions running tourism programmes in Nigeria need to introduce self -assessment of programmes and not rely on the NBTE accreditation which comes up in three years. Also there is need for a staff development policy that will encourage Tourism educators to further their education; The Tertiary Educational Trust Fund (TETFUND) should focus on developing staff of tourism education because it is an area of study in Nigeria that lacks qualified personnel. With the way higher institution in Nigeria are finding interest in tourism programmes, having good quality programmes will not only produce better professionals but it will help in offering better services in the industry and maximizing the impacts of the business.

Keywords—Education, evaluation tourism, quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

EDUCATION is said to be basic instruction in knowledge acquisition and gaining thorough understanding of ideas [1]. Peters as cited by [2] elaborates that change must occur by attaining a transformed outlook on life. Information learnt must be translated into new ways of seeing and doing things. Reference [1] explains that education is a direct instruction in Knowledge and skills aimed to facilitate people to make the most of time in every aspect of life. Reference [3] opined that education is a process which exposes the individuals' talent Tourism education started over some decades ago, [4] explains that the study of tourism can be traced to the study of some of the major elements in the tourism sector specifically, hotel operations and catering activities as leisure and recreation. One of the important influences on the growth of Tourism was Medliks report in 1966 which states the position and location of tourism programmes. Reference [5] described tourism studies as a course that have a tendency to take the personality of the specific knowledge of existing work which may result in a certain subject learning. Reference [6] sees Tourism education as an area that is small, very much vocational and business controlled area of study which is

related to more recognized fields of investigation with its own different types of literature, specialist and curriculum coverage. The curriculum forms a basic part of tourism education, [7] expatiates that different tourism curriculums have been designed by tourism educators with small or the absence of specialist from the industry [29]. It is required that a number of individuals, as well as groups of individuals have to interact for mutual benefits justifying the idea of stakeholder management in educational settings. Reference [8] states that institutional managers may rely on the decisions of policy makers in order to implement strategies in their institutions. Lecturers may rely on such strategies to determine the peculiarities of the modules that they teach [9]. The importance of the curriculum is illustrated by [10] as follows, a well-developed curriculum has provided improved basis in higher education quality.

Nigeria is a country that has different types of higher institutions of learning; the higher education consists of universities, polytechnics and colleges of education [11]. There are one hundred and eighteen universities in Nigeria, out of which only eleven offer tourism programmes, some of the institutions running the programmes are not yet accredited by the Nigeria university commission. Also, there are seventy five polytechnics in Nigeria only eleven offer courses in tourism.

Reference [12] states the inability of the programmes to get accredited by the National Board for Technical education in Nigeria and the National university commission is a cause for concern. Reference [13] identifies that in 2011 only three national diploma programmes and one higher national diploma programmes were accredited. Reference [14] highlights the quality of Nigeria higher institutions are very poor; there are inadequate learning facilities, unqualified personnel and poor funding of the institutions. Some experts, e.g. [10] maintain that it is important that these problems are solved so that quality is maintained in tourism education.

Reference [15] says in order to prepare tourism graduates to enter the critical business of tourism, the goal for tourism education should be to provide a learning environment that reflects what is in the industry. Reference [16] explains that tourism educators should strive to provide technical skills, knowledge and theoretical and conceptual knowledge of tourism. The quality of educators appear to be what is seriously lacking in hospitality and tourism education. Reference [17] illustrates that problems of educators using old teaching methods affect the performers of the students in the industry. Reference [18] states how it is important to highlight that current approaches to quality in higher education often

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represent a move towards management styles that promote performance indicators culture within institutions of higher learning. Tourism educators in Nigeria are facing the problem of development through furthering their education and this affects their approaches to delivering quality education. Existing research of [19] have talked about tourism education in different countries of Europe, Asia, America and few African countries, there has not been much written on tourism education in West Africa. Therefore this paper aims to evaluate the quality of tourism education in Nigeria and offer suggestions on how best it can be improved.

Looking at the above-mentioned issues on quality of tourism education in Nigeria, this paper aimed at evaluating the quality of tourism education in Nigeria higher institutions. The paper also came up with the following questions:

- What is the quality of tourism education in Nigeria?
- In what ways can tourism education in Nigeria be improved?

II. RELATED WORKS

Reference [17] opined that for quality to be attained in tourism education, evaluation is very important. Reference [20] states the main types of evaluation of a programme in higher education are: programme evaluation, subject evaluation, programme accreditation, programme benchmarking and subject benchmarking. Reference [9] further explains that evaluation of programme gives more attention to the quality of the activities lined up for learning in the programme of study [20]. Accreditation is similar to evaluation because the same methodology is used; however, accreditation is not the same with evaluation because it involves benchmarking assessment [21]. Accreditation does not involve self-evaluation [22]. A programme can be evaluated to improve quality in education by having feedback from stakeholders who are current students, graduates and employers.

While criteria for evaluation differ between institutions and countries the main principles remain the same [23]. There is more on the explanations on the procedures as given by Moir and Hodgkin's [23] which states guaranteeing academic excellence is certain by the development and design of the curriculum, maintaining good students experience in the class rooms and monitoring the way knowledge is transmitted to the students and performance of courses through assessment. Reference [9] elaborates that there should be resources designed to ensure good learning and teaching processes.

The university education is seen by students to be an asset for an impending career and longs for its monetary return [9]. Diplomas and certificates are of great significance to those that graduated from a tourism programme, this help the graduates to be equipped to face the challenges in the tourism industry. Reference [24] elaborates that educators must always consider the issue of concept delivery in tourism education; this is to give clear consideration to the graduates which make

them to be very competent employees when they start working after their education. Reference [9] argues that what is worth taking into consideration by tourism educators is whether employment is the single significant reason for undertaking education in tourism. Although [25] argues that the above points create reasonable worries because tourism is quite an emerging area of learning in higher education has had to cope with some issues from an educational viewpoint. The work further says the role of educators should not be limited to making students employable in future.

The relevance of achieving higher qualification in tourism is seen in two ways by [26]. Firstly, there is the need for educators to have a higher certificate either masters, or doctorate to maintain or raise future career prospects. The second reason is for some educators with up to doctoral degree in other fields of study teaching tourism classes, these individuals need to undergo conversion courses in degrees or short term professional development. This therefore, shows how significant furthering tourism education is to both tourism practitioners and tourism educators as stating in a finding by Buba [19].

Reference [3] finds out the criteria for evaluating tourism education which is applicable to most higher institutions have been stated in a way that it will measure the effectiveness of the academic system, likewise the way tourism programmes are incorporated to the tourism industry and to meet the educational needs of the students. Reference [27] states that it is important to use evaluation and accreditation as criteria for evaluating tourism education. Reference [28] explains that academic facilities used in teaching students such as library and classroom materials need to be evaluated on a regular basis to reflect the unique nature of the tourism industry. Another way of evaluating tourism education is by assessing students in the following ways: "Attractiveness of the tourism programme for students: financial and administrative procedures, communication. Relationship with students: Admissions criteria, academic and administrative management and financial and administrative management and complementary services. [9] Assessment of student; Determination of student satisfaction, industry acceptance and academic file administration [21, p. 156], [22]. The aim of the programme must meet the intended learning outcomes and what students intend to achieve during the study of the programme.

Nigeria has national regulatory bodies for evaluating quality in higher institutions of learning, the agencies are NUC established in 1964 and NBTE established in 1977 [11]. Educational programmes in Nigeria are accredited by setting up minimum standards against which programmes are evaluated [14]. Reference [12] says pre accreditation activities must be carried out before accreditation of a programme, this entails meeting up the minimum academic standards. These standards include Stakeholder participatory process, staff facilities, course content, course delivery and evaluation. For a programme to merit being accredited it must have been approved by the NBTE or THE NUC to run for two years to ensure the programme matures before accreditation.

III. METHODS

Being a longitudinal study, this research used qualitative data from secondary sources. Secondary data were collected from the National board for technical education. These include list of institutions and accredited tourism programmes. Information on the training of tourism educators and their qualifications was obtained from reports of the boards and examined, data on evaluation criteria for the tourism programmes were found from the regulatory agency.

The paper used the archival strategy this is because of the reason stated by [29]. The work of [29] states that archival research make use of administrative vital information and documents as the major source of data for a study [30]. The researcher adopted the strategy because the existing documents used for the study are reports written by professionals in the field of tourism who carried out the evaluation of the polytechnics running tourism courses in Nigeria. Saunders et al. [29] further stated that the term archival can be referred to recent of historical documents [30]. The word archival can mean historical, it can also be referred to present documents in an organisation. Archived data as a basis for secondary analysis is not only in relation to historical study of the past, it involves the present too, data archiving offers opportunity for generalisation of findings to wide practical or political populations [31]. Archival research uses administrative documents as a principal source of data [29]. "Documents are standardised artefacts in so far as they typically occur in particular formats; as notes, reports, contracts, drafts, death certificates, remarks, diaries, statistics, certificates, judgements, letters or expert opinions" [32, p. 284].

Source of data for this study is based on documents that have been in existence in the organisations responsible for regulating higher education in Nigeria. The paper used the documents that were written for official use as explained by [29]. The reports submitted by the accreditation team to the NBTE were the documents used for the study; the reports were studied and vital data were derived to achieve the objective that deals with evaluating tourism education in Nigeria. The reports were for accreditation of different programmes in the country which includes both HND and ND programmes. The criteria for the evaluation were identified in the reports and the reports stated whether the institutions met the criteria or not.

The paper adopted the non-probability sampling because the technique is used based on the researcher's judgment regarding those of the population's characteristics that are important in relation to the data required to address the research aim as illustrated by [33] and [34]. Homogeneous purposive sampling as elaborated by Saunders et al. [29] which focuses on choosing one particular sub-group, such as a particular occupation or level in an organization's hierarchy. Characteristics of such participants are similar allowing these to be explored in greater depth and minor differences to be more apparent were used. There are currently eleven universities and eleven polytechnics that run tourism programmes in Nigeria [19]. The study focused on the HND

and ND programmes in the polytechnics. Reports of the accreditation of tourism programmes which is the only evaluation criteria used for tourism programmes in Nigeria is sampled from 1995-2011. Twenty reports of accreditation of HND and ND programmes were sampled from the eleven polytechnics in the country. The instrument used is an evaluation form formulated by the researcher, to assess teaching and evaluation, programme resources and student support and management of human resources and student enrolment. The reason for the choice of the polytechnics for this study is because, tourism education started from the polytechnics in the mid-seventies, the universities started running the programme in the year 2000 and there are still some universities that have not yet graduated tourism students. Using the polytechnic gives the researcher a better insight of the problem.

Data was analysed through quantitative data analysis as stated by Saunders et al. [29] these are data that do not contain numbers or data that have not been computed and can be used for all research strategies. Data from the evaluation reports were analysed using the SPSS, the average mean score were used to determine the quality for each standard for teaching and evaluation, effective human resource and student enrolment, quality of programme resources and student support.

IV. RESULTS

The data for the evaluation of quality of tourism programme in Nigeria is presented on Tables I-III. The data involves the different criteria for evaluation adopted for the purpose of the study. The rating of the data is through average mean score of 1-5; 1= very poor quality, 2=poor quality, 3=fair quality, 4= good quality and 5=very good quality. The average response of each item from the 20 evaluation reports are presented to rate the quality of tourism education. While percentages are used for the frequency distribution and yearly evaluation of the data.

TABLE I
 QUALITY OF TEACHING AND EVALUATION

Item	N. Valid	Mean
Practical coverage	20	2.45
Dissertation quality	20	3.00
Coverage of exam questions	20	2.90
Standard of exam question	20	3.10
Developed marking scheme	20	3.25
Student assessment & feedback	20	2.20
Mastery of theory & practical	20	3.40
Examination Success rate	20	3.45
External moderator	20	3.30
Employers rating	20	3.90
New tech. in teaching & learning	20	1.20

Source: Buba (2012) [19]

Table I shows the quality of teaching and evaluation of students. The coverage of practical as stated in the curriculum has an average mean score of 2.45 which is below fair quality. The quality of student's dissertations has an average mean score of 3.00 which represents fair quality result. The coverage of test and examinations has an average mean score

of 2.90 which is a little below fair quality result. The standard of examination questions average mean score is 3.10 which is fair quality. Well-developed marking scheme has 3.25 as average mean score which is a fair quality result. Students demonstration of mastering the practical and theory has an average mean score of 3.40 which is a little above a fair quality result. The success rates of students is a little above fair quality result with the average mean score of 3.45. Qualified external moderator has an average mean of 3.30 which is fair quality. The employers rating of the programme is good with 3.90 as average mean score. The use of new technologies for teaching and evaluation is 1.20 which is poor result. The total average mean for teaching and evaluation is 2.92 which is poor quality; the result shows that the quality of teaching and evaluation is poor.

TABLE II
 QUALITY OF PROGRAMME RESOURCES AND STUDENT SUPPORT

Item	N. Valid	Mean
Classroom & L. theatres	20	3.75
Tourism Village	20	2.60
Accommodation	20	2.65
Ticketing office	20	2.65
Staff offices	20	3.85
Clean learning environment	20	3.70
Facilities for student practical	20	1.15
IT services	20	1.00
Electronic and print books	20	1.00
Electronic and print Journals	20	1.00
Toilet facilities	20	1.50
Student support programme	20	1.50

Source: Buba (2012) [19]

The data on the quality of programme resources and student support is presented on Table II. The classroom/lecture theatre facilities have an average mean score of 3.75 representing fairly good facilities. Tourism village; a place built for tourism practical with accommodation facilities, ticketing office, museum and recreational facilities in higher institutions running tourism programmes. Tourism house (accommodation part of the tourism village) has 2.65 as average mean score representing a poor quality result. The ticketing office has an average mean of 2.65 representing poor quality result. Staff offices are fairly good in quality with an average mean score of 3.85. Clean learning environment has average mean score of 3.70 which represents a fairly good quality. Adequate facilities for student practical as stated in the curriculum have average mean score of 1.15 representing a very poor result. ICT facilities for learning have a mean score of 1.00 which is very poor. Available electronic and printed books for the programme have a mean score of 1.00 which is very poor. Available printed and electronic journals for the programme have a mean score of 1.00 which is a very poor result. Available toilet facilities have a mean score of 1.50 which is very poor. Students support programme has a mean score of 1.50 which represents a very poor result. The total average mean score for quality of student programme resources and student support is 2.20 indicating poor quality.

TABLE III
 MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES AND STUDENT ENROLMENT

Item	N. Valid	Mean
Qualified teaching staff	20	2.15
Required workload	20	1.90
Overload workload	20	1.65
Less workload	20	2.35
Staff dev. Policy	20	3.20
Student entry requirement	20	3.50
Student carrying capacity	20	2.75

Source: Buba (2012) [19]

The data presented in Table III is for the effective management of human resources and student enrolment. The variable on qualified teaching staff has average mean score of 2.15 representing a poor academic qualification for the academic staff teaching the various tourism programmes, the report shows very few academic staff with postgraduate qualification in tourism related fields. Academic staff required work load is very low with a mean of 1.90, the evaluation reports show that academic staff do not take the required work load applicable for each staff position. Less work load has a mean of 2.35 which represents academic staff have less work hour. The staff work overload shows a mean of 1.65 which shows that very few staffs have over work load. The staff development policy in various institutions is fair with average mean of 3.20. The entry requirements for students are fairly good with a mean score of 3.50, the reports show list of students admitted into some tourism programmes with deficiency in Mathematics and English. Student's carrying capacity is poor, with the programmes exceeding its carrying capacity; the average mean score is 2.75. The total average means score for effective management of human resources and students' enrolment is 2.50 which indicate a poor quality in that area.

V. DISCUSSION

The results for the quality of teaching is poor, practical are not covered as stated in the curriculum. The teaching staffs do not teach the students the stated number of practical in the curriculum depriving them of gaining the required knowledge. Each topic has at least a practical to be carried out in the classrooms or in the ticketing office, tourism village or on field trip. The findings is not in accordance with the criteria stated by [13] which says Student's dissertation should have a clearly defined aim and objectives and have acceptable methodology for it execution. Practical should be relevant to the programme and tourism profession. Though many scholars have debated on what makes a good teaching experience, [4] states that attention needs to be focussed on what makes a good learning experience. The findings on the quality of dissertation is fair, it shows that some of the criteria's of having a good dissertation as stated in accreditation guideline [13] are met. Examinations question are supposed to be of standard covering all the units of the curriculum, the study found out that examination questions do not cover all the units of the curriculum, though many argue on examination being the best way of assessing students, [34] is in support of having

students evaluated in the areas of their study. The reports show a fairly good success rate in the results of the students, the institutions have external moderators though most of the moderators are not academics but tourism practitioners. Having non academics to moderate academic work may not be effective as the moderators have little or no knowledge on teaching and evaluation. The report revealed that the sample of students interviewed showed understanding of the contents of the curriculum, this is why the findings on the employers rating of the performance of the graduates of the programme as good, the result is in agreement with [16] who states that tourism graduates should be able to practice what is learnt in the tourism industry. Good teaching makes students to develop themselves beyond the business of tourism according to a study in 2008 [35]; if students are not well taught the content of the curriculum they may find it difficult to master the knowledge impacted.

The reports on student assessment and feedback show a poor result. The teaching staffs do not follow their marking scheme in awarding marks to the students. There is no feedback for the students to improve in areas of their weaknesses. Most of the marks are lumped together. The findings do not agree with [13] who opined that feedback should be given for students to improve. The programme lacks new technology for teaching and evaluation; the findings shows that the use new technology for teaching and evaluation is very poor, all the institutions use the traditional blackboard and chalk, there is no provision for access to the internet for students learning. Students are taught bookings and reservations in theory; there is no provision for computers for students to explore for learning. All the institutions do not have the software for plagiarism. Students copy work from passed works or/and their colleagues without being detected. These findings do not agree with the theories of [16] which states that a curriculum should give provision for the use of new technologies in learning. The work of [35] states that students are not kept up to date on tourism activities if teaching is not properly carried out. The tourism industry is growing rapidly and the teachers should have the ability to communicate in a way that there is understanding on the part of the learners.

The resources of the programme and student support are very important in tourism education. The availability of teaching facilities enhances the quality of knowledge as stated by [9] students need support for the duration of their study. The support can be in form personal tutors, course advisers, student liaison and counselling. The findings of the study show that classrooms and lecture theatres are fairly good in quality. This is because of the involvement of the educational trust fund that is providing learning facilities in learning institutions. The Tourism village is fairly for all tourism programmes in Nigeria, it consist of tourists accommodation, ticketing office and tourism museum. The facilities in the tourism villages are for tourism practical as stated in the tourism curriculum. Though all the institutions meet the criteria for having tourism village, the findings shows poor facilities; most of the tourism villages are not equipped with

the necessary facilities for learning. Those that have the required facilities do not have enough to meet the capacity of the students; for instance, none of the tourism villages have more than four computers in the ticketing rooms. The available facilities are either faulty or not functioning due to power failure. This findings is in agreement with [36] which states that though resources are foundation for quality in education, programme resources alone is not enough to offer good quality of learning experience. The use of information and communication technology in learning cannot be over emphasised, [27] states that learning is easier if the required resources are available. The study of [16] finds out that however good students are, they need quality educational facilities to perfect their learning.

Student supports are practiced in all the programmes, but the level of support given to the student is poor. The type of support given is course advisers, who help in giving academic related advice to students and compiling student results. Though some institutions of learning have guidance and counselling units who give support to students. There is no support as personal tutor, academic liaison office and a student support office to help students. What the institutions have is student affairs unit which is responsible for student accommodation and student union. The findings did not support that of [19] and [37] which states that support to students help them academically. There should be guidance on how students can understand what is being taught rather than only acquiring the skills. Furthermore, [38] States that educators should make students see themselves outside the tourism industry.

Teacher's activities and qualification can reflect in courses taught and improve students' learning experience [39]. The results of the study show that human resource management is poor, though all the programmes have a staff development policy. Teaching staff are not involved in wide range of academic activities like seminars, workshops and government sponsored projects to increase their professional knowledge. The teaching qualification is poor as only few staffs have MSc. In Tourism related programme. The findings show no staffs currently hold a PhD in Tourism. The findings does not agree with [40] which are of the opinion that any successful tourism programme must have quality and development of academic staff both as teachers and researchers.

The entry requirements for the students is fairly good, as the result of the findings shows that programmes stick to the entry requirement laid down by NBTE, though there are few students with deficiencies in English Language and Mathematics. This findings may have implications on the quality of education because deficiency shows weaknesses and such weaknesses can contribute to failure on the part of the students. Student success rate which was low could be as a result of having student with low entry requirements. Teachers with low educational qualification will not teach students effectively and therefore, they are not vast in knowledge of tourism.

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE WORK

After evaluating the quality of tourism education in Nigeria, this paper has the following suggestions for improvement on the poor aspect of tourism education in Nigeria.

There is need for the programme to get involved in self-evaluation of tourism programmes, so as to ensure that quality is being maintained in all areas of education. The institutions should not wait till after three years for NBTE to evaluate the programmes.

There should be a staff development policy that will encourage staff to further their education; The Educational Trust Fund (ETF) should focus on developing staff of tourism education because it is an area of study in Nigeria that lacks qualified personnel. Academic staff can be sponsored to universities in the United Kingdom who are good in tourism education, since the system of education in Nigeria is similar to that of the United Kingdom.

There is need for introduction of new technology for teaching and evaluation in the higher institutions; the ICT system in the institutions should be developed and software's for plagiarism detection should be provided. More computers should be made available for staff and students and provision should be made for the availability of online materials for learning.

There should be improvement on student support from the normal course coordinator support. The idea of personal tutor should be introduced to help the students when having difficulties in learning. Each faculty should have a student support office where various help can be rendered to students.

Though the institutions run guidance and counselling units for support students; there should be support as personal tutor, academic liaison office and a student support office to help students when they have challenges in the process of their studies.

VII. CONCLUSION

Tourism education in Nigeria is a field of study that is lacking behind, the tourism industry in Nigeria is growing fast, thus the need for effective tourism education in the higher institutions of learning. The world is going global which gives need for introduction of new technology for learning in schools. The success of tourism education in Nigeria depends on the major stakeholders involved. Government must show seriousness in provision of facilities for education and staff development. Educators must work hard to see that they develop themselves in the area of tourism. The students also need to show commitment to learning by studying. Though the paper adopted different procedures for evaluating quality, there are some research limitations. The study uses only the polytechnics in Nigeria, which may limit the possibility of generalising the findings. Nevertheless, the approach and the results of the study provide a good understanding of quality of tourism education which can be used in other countries apart from Nigeria.

The paper does not include curriculum, student's achievements, administrative management, staff performance

and strategic funding. This may limit the items as the areas above have tremendous effect on quality of education. However, teaching and evaluation, human resource and student enrolment and programme resources and student support are important areas of education that can effect student performance in the industry, society and enhance tourism knowledge.

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